

Amidation of Hyaluronan through Chemical Modifications Using DMTMM Activation

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Abstract: The modification of hyaluronic acid with functional amines enhances its properties for biomedical applications by introducing specific molecular functionalities. Here, we report the synthesis of piperonylamine-modified hyaluronic acid using 4-(4,6-dimethoxy-1,3,5-triazin-2-yl)-4-methylmorpholinium chloride (DMTMM) as a coupling agent. The reaction conditions were optimized to achieve a degree of substitution (DS) of 50%, confirmed by comprehensive characterization. Proton nuclear magnetic resonance (NMR) spectroscopy provided structural validation, while gel permeation chromatography (GPC) analysis indicated successful modification without significant degradation of the polymer backbone. This modification imparts unique characteristics to the HA derivative, making it a promising candidate for applications in targeted drug delivery and tissue engineering.

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I. Introduction

Hyaluronic acid (HA) is a natural polymer that is widely used in biomedical applications due to its outstanding biocompatibility, swelling properties, and adjustable mechanical characteristics [1]. HA is a macromolecule with a high molecular weight, ranging from 1000 to 6 million Daltons, and it belongs to the glycosaminoglycan family. Its structure is made up of two sugar-based components—N-acetylglucosamine and D-glucuronic acid—that combine to form a repeating disaccharide polymer [2-3]. These components are connected through alternating β -1,4 and β -1,3 glycosidic bonds (see Figure 1). Derivatives of hyaluronic acid serve as the foundation for various anti-adhesion gels [4].

When chemically modified, hyaluronic acid (HA) can take place various physical forms, such as viscoelastic solutions, hydrogels, flexible sheets, and nanoparticulate fluids. These modifications can change the properties of the material, resulting in variations in hydrophobicity and biological activity. The resulting products are utilized in a wide array of clinical and preclinical applications [5].

Several strategies have been developed for modifying hyaluronic acid (HA) through its carboxyl and hydroxyl groups [6–8]. Chemical modification of HA offers options for its use as a biomaterial in medical applications. The physical properties of HA can be altered by attaching pendant groups and through crosslinking. Various pendant groups, including benzyl and alkyl groups, have been linked to the carboxyl group of HA [9].

Chemical modifications of hyaluronic acid (HA) can be achieved by either coupling specific substances to the polysaccharide chain or by creating crosslinks between the chains. The crosslinking of HA is necessary in order to form injectable hydrogels since non modified HA solutions

are rapidly degraded in the body. The tissue half-life of HA-based implants is increased from hours or days to months or even years with the appropriate modifications [10-12]. Common modification reactions include carbodiimide-mediated reactions, bis-epoxide crosslinking, and crosslinking with divinyl sulfone [13].

Figure 1: Structure of Hyaluronic acid.

II. Material and methods

Hyaluronan, sodium salt (cosmetic grade) was purchased from Caesar and Loretz GmbH, piperonylamine, 2-chloro-4,6-dimethoxy-1,3,5-triazine (CDMT), N-methyl morpholine (NMM), Dialysis membrane cutoff 14000 Dalton were purchased from sigma Aldrich company.

Synthesis of 4-(4,6-Dimethoxy-1,3,5-triazin-2-yl)-4-methylmorpholinium Chloride (DMTMM)

The compound was prepared as described in the literature [14]. (NMM) (4.04 g, 40 mmol) was added to a solution of (CDMT) (7.72 g, 44 mmol) in THF (120 mL) at room temperature. A white solid precipitate appeared within several minutes. After stirring for 1 Hour at room temperature, the solid was collected by suction filtration and washed with THF and dried under vacuum to give DMTMM (10.93 g, 98.7%). The purity of DMTMM is good enough for condensation at this point.

$^1\text{H-NMR}$ (Methanol- d_4) 3.55 (s, 3 H), 3.82-3.95 (m, 4 H), 4.07-4.10 (m, 2 H), 4.19 (s, 6 H), 4.53-4.6 (m, 2 H).

$^{13}\text{C-NMR}$ (Methanol- d_4) 55.1, 56.3, 60.3, 62, 171 and 174.

Synthesis of piperonylamine modified hyaluronic acid

Sodium hyaluronate (500 mg, 1.24 mmole) was dissolved overnight in deionized water, DMTMM (344.8 mg, 1.25 mmole) was added to clear Sodium Hyaluronate solution, after 15 minutes of stirring, piperonylamine (95.23 mg, 0.63 mmole) was added dropwise to the mixture and was stirred overnight. Modified HA was precipitated in 5-fold excess of Ethanol, the precipitate was redissolved in deionized water and dialysis 5 times against water. At last, piperonylamine-HA was isolated by freeze-drying.

Figure 2: ^1H NMR spectra of modified HA in D_2O

mV

Figure 3: GPC Chromatogram of modified HA

III. Results and discussion

^1H -Nuclear magnetic resonance spectroscopy

In this study, the degree of substitution (DS) of modified Hyaluronic acid was confirmed by NMR characterization of 1 mg of modified hyaluronic acid in 600 μL of D_2O solvent.

The signals at δ 6.95 and 5.99 were assigned to the hydrogen atoms of piperonylamine, while the signal at δ 2.04 was attributed to the acetyl group of hyaluronic acid (HA), indicating a successful connection between piperonylamine and HA (see Figure 2).

GPC/SEC Analysis of modified Hyaluronic Acid

The chromatogram of the modified hyaluronic acid (HA) indicates the purity of the product, with a peak observed at 11.645 min. The analysis was performed with GPC equipped with refractive index detector using SUPREMA, 8 x 300 mm column and Na_2SO_4 solution as mobile phase at elution rate of 0.5 mL/min. (see Figure 3).

IV. Conclusions

In conclusion, the successful modification of hyaluronic acid with piperonylamine using DMTMM as a coupling agent has introduced valuable functional properties to the polymer, as confirmed by NMR and GPC analyses. The optimized reaction conditions resulted in a high degree of substitution and preserved the structural integrity of the polymer. Additionally, samples with varying degrees of substitution (DS) will be synthesized. Future analyses, including physicochemical surface characterization, biocompatibility and microbiological studies, will provide further insights into the suitability of the modified hyaluronic acid for biomedical applications. This work lays a solid foundation for its potential use in targeted drug delivery and tissue engineering until ongoing evaluations are completed.

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